

**TARIXIY-NAZARIY MANBALARDA TURLI TAHDIDLARGA QARSHI
KURASH MASALASI TAHLILI VA HOZIRGI DAVRDA GLOBAL INTERNET
TAHDIDLARINING O‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI VA ULARGA QARSHI KURASH
ZARURIYATI.**

Mo‘ydinov Asilbek Adxam o‘g‘li

Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar kafedrasasi o‘qtuvchisi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8026707>

Annotatsiya. Mamlakatimiz yoshlari o‘rtasida ularning ma’naviy tarbiyasiga oid so‘rovnomalar o‘tkazilgan, bu esa yoshlar ongida kechayotgan jarayonlarni chuqurroq ochib berishda muxim rol o‘ynaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: qarashlar, manbalar, kurash, internet, tahdid.

**ANALYSIS OF THE ISSUE OF COMBATING VARIOUS THREATS IN
HISTORICAL-THEORETICAL SOURCES AND THE PECULIARITIES OF
GLOBAL INTERNET THREATS IN THE CURRENT PERIOD AND THE NEED
TO COMBAT THEM.**

Abstract. Surveys have been conducted among the youth of our country regarding their spiritual education, which plays a role of Mukhim in the deeper disclosure of the processes taking place in the minds of young people.

Key words: views, resources, struggle, internet, threat.

**АНАЛИЗ ВОПРОСА БОРЬБЫ С РАЗЛИЧНЫМИ УГРОЗАМИ В
ИСТОРИКО-ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИХ ИСТОЧНИКАХ И СПЕЦИФИКИ ГЛОБАЛЬНЫХ
ИНТЕРНЕТ-УГРОЗ В СОВРЕМЕННУЮ ЭПОХУ И НЕОБХОДИМОСТИ БОРЬБЫ
С НИМИ.**

Аннотация. Среди молодежи нашей страны проведены опросы, касающиеся их духовного воспитания, что играет важную роль в более глубоком раскрытии процессов, происходящих в сознании молодежи.

Ключевое слова: взгляды, ресурсы, борьба, интернет, угроза.

Xalqimiz o‘tmishida ham tahdidlar bo‘lgan, biroq xalqimiz va muttafakkirlarimiz ularga munosib qarshilik ko‘rsatib kelishgan.

Moturidiylik ta’limotining asoschisi Abu Mansur al-Moturidiydir. Abu Mansur al-Moturidiy (870-944) Samarqandning Moturid qishlog‘ida tug‘ilgan. U dastlabki ta’limni o‘zining qishlog‘ida olib, keyinchalik Samarqanddagi Raboti g‘oziyon madrasasida davom ettirdi. Al-Moturidiy yashagan davr somoniylar hukmronlik qilgan davrga to‘g‘ri keladi. Ma’lumki, Somoniylarning hukmronlik davrida markazlashgan davlat shakllangan. Buning asosiy sabablaridan biri ajdodlarimiz chetdan kirib kelayotgan tahdidlarga qarshi munosib qarshilik ko‘rsata olishgan.

Narshaxiyning “Buxoro tarixi” asarida keltirilishicha, “... amir Ismoil Somoniy xalqni (bu qiyinchilikni tortishdan) ozod qildi va devor ham xarob bo‘ldi, Amir: «To men tirik ekanman, Buxoro viloyatining devori men bo‘laman»,— dedi va ustiga olgan bu vazifani to‘la bajardi; u doimo janglarda o‘zi qatnashdi va Buxoro viloyati ustidan dushmanlarning zafar topishlariga yo‘l qo‘ymadi”. Ismoil Somoniy o‘z so‘zlari bilan xalqning ishonchini qozongan va ana shu ruhiy madad tufayli markazlashgan davlat tuza olgan.

Rennesans davrida ham diniy masalalarga oid g'oyaviy va ma'naviy tahdidlar turli maqsadlarda suqilib kirishga uringan.

Al-Moturidiy "Ta'vilot al-Qur'on" asarida Abu Hanifaning qarashlariga suyangan holda buzg'unchi g'oyalarni rad qilishga harakat qiladi .

Olmon olimi Ulrix Rudolf Moturidiy ilmiy merosini Ash'ariy ta'limoti bilan solishtirar ekan, ularning o'rtasidagi muayyan o'xshashliklarning mavjud ekanligini e'tirof etadi. Shu bilan birga, ba'zi farqlar ham uchrashi va ular eng muhim tamoyillarga tegishli ekanini aniqladi. Avvalo shuni aytish kerakki, ularning sunnatga munosabatida hamfikrlik yo'q. Chunki Ash'ariy boshda, mu'taziliy olimi edi, keyinchalik namoyishkorona, Ulrix Rudolf ifodasicha, balki itoatkorona, hanbaliylar tomoniga o'tdi. Moturidiy esa sharqiy hanafiylikning namoyondasi edi va umrining oxirigacha shunday bo'lib qoldi.

Ash'ariy o'z nazariyasini dalillash uchun radikal ta'riflar keltirishdan qaytmagan. Moturidiy esa, aksincha, radikallikdan qochgan. U ko'proq barchani qoniqtiruvchi, shu bilan birga islom asoslariga muvofiq keluvchi sintezlash yo'lini afzal ko'rgan .

Moturidiy haqidagi dastlabki ma'lumotlar, tabiiyki uning vatani-Movarounahrda paydo bo'lgan. Bu yerda hijriy V / milodiy XI asrga kelib, Moturidiy ta'siri shakllangan edi. Uning zamondoshlari o'z ilohiy an'analari haqida jiddiy o'ylay boshladilar. Ushbu an'analarni shakllantirishda qo'shgan uning hissasi hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan degan xulosaga kelindi. Abulyusr al-Pazdaviy (vafoti xijriy 493/ milodiy 1100 yil) xuddi shu mazmundagi mulohazani bildiradi, uning zamondoshi Abulmu'in an-Nasafiy (vafoti hijriy 508/ milodiy 1114y.) esa aynan shu fikrni yorqinroq ifoda etadi . Ammo ularning birontasi ham Moturidiyning Movarounahrdagi sunniy ilohiyotning asoschisi deb e'lon qilish niyatini ko'zlamaydi. Ular Moturidiyga ko'proq o'zlarning atoqli hamkasbi, ya'ni mavjud ilohiy ta'limotni qoyilmaqom bayon etgan va sharhlagan mutafakkir sifatida qaraydilar. Abu Hanifaga esa ushbu maktabning asoschisi sifatida qaraganlar. U diniy ta'limotning barcha asosiy masalalari bo'yicha nimaiki degan bo'lsa, haqiqat sifatida qabul qilinishi, nimaniki targ'ib etgan bo'lsa, hech qanday o'zgarishsiz yetkazilishi va talqin etilishi lozim edi.

Pazdaviyda bu niyat ikkiyoqlama namoyon bo'lgan. U bir tomondan o'z e'tiqodini moturidiya deb emas, balki ongli ravishda ashobi Abu Hanifa deb atagan . Ikkinchi tomondan, u yoki bu nazariya Abu Hanifa ta'limotida allaqachonlar majud ekanini qayta-qayta ta'kidlashga uringan.

Biz bilamizki, taniqli Abulyusr al-Pazdaviyning katta bobosi Abdulkarim bin Muso al-Pazdaviy (v.390/999y.) Moturidiy qo'lida ta'lim olgan. Abulyusr al-Pazdaviy Moturidiy to'g'risidagi ayrim tafsilotlarni o'zining katta bobosi Abdulkarimdan shaxsan otasi Muhammad orqali bilgan. Moturidiy haqida eng qimmatli ma'lumotlarni bergan Abulyusr al-Pazdaviyning ta'kidlashicha, Moturidiy zohid bo'lgan, binobarin, undan ko'p karomatlar zohir bo'lgani Pazdaviylar urug'ida uzoq vaqt hikoya qilib yurilgan. Qashqadaryo viloyatidagi Ko'hna Fazli qo'rg'onida yashagan Bazdaviylar sulolasi vakillari orasida islom fiqhi (huquqshunosligi) to'g'risidagi izlanishlar davomiyligi bir necha asrlar davomida saqlangan.

Abulyusr al-Pazdaviy qoldirgan guvohlik o'zining ma'no va ifodalarining ancha aniqligi bilan diqqatga sazovor. U o'z shaxsiy ilohiyot an'anasini yorqin anglagani bilan ajralib turadi. Pazdaviy o'z nazariyasini nafaqat bid'atlardan, balki o'z nomiga ega boshqa maktablardan alohida ajratishni istar edi. Bunday yondashuv o'z maqsadlariga binoan tanlangan nufuzli olimlarga ochiq

va to'g'ridan to'g'ri murojaat qilishni talab qilar edi. Pazdaviy ularning ayrim fikrlarini so'zma-so'z keltirgan. Bu hol ayniqsa, "Kitob al-olim"ga nisbatan ochiq ko'rinadi. "Kitob al-olim"ni Pazdaviy "Usul"da tilga olgan. Kitobning to'liq nomi "Kitob al-olim va-l-mutaallim" ("Ustoz va shogird") bo'lib, u Abu Muqotil As-Samaqandiy (v.208/823y.) qalamiga mansubligi bahsli munozaradan so'ng aniqlangan .

Qariyb bir vaqtning o'zida al-Nasafiyning zamondoshi Abu al-Yusir al-Pazdaviy (vafoti milodiy 1100 yil) o'zining "Usul ad-din" asarida al-Moturidiy haqida ham ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Unda ko'proq maqto'vlar va Moturidiyning kalom borasidagi fikrlari bayon etilgan .

Abu al-Yusir al-Pazdaviy "Usul ad-din" kitobida keltirilishicha, "Ta'vilot" – shu sohada tengi yo'q kitob.... Bu sohada ilgari asar yozgan mualliflarning birortasi ham buning darajasiga yetisha olmagandir.

Abu Toxirxoja "Samariya" nomli asarida quyidagilarni keltirib o'tadi: - Ushbu imom otasining oti Husayndir. Ali Pazdaviy 10 jildlik "Mabsut" kitobi, "Jome' us-sag'ir" sharhi hamda usuli fiqhda "Usuli Pazdaviy" kitoblarini yozgan. Derlarkim, shu imomning zamonasida Shofe'iy mazhabida bo'lgan bir olim kelib, hanafiy mazhabidagi olimlarni yenga boshladi va o'z mazhabiga kirgizaverdi. Mullalar uning bilan munozara qilishga undab imomga yopishdilar. Imom ko'nmadi. Lekin mullalar firib ishlatib uni munozara qildirdilar. Shofe'iy olimi imom Shofe'iyini maqtab, u bir oyda "Qur'on"ni yodlagandir, dedi. Imom: "Bu juda qulay bir ish, olti oyda el aro tarqalgan butun ilmlardan xabardor bo'lmak mumkin", dedi. Olti oydan keyin qaysi kitobdan so'rasalar, (Ali Pazdaviy) mufassal yo'sinda aytib berar edi. Shofe'iy olimi bu holni ko'rgach, inday olmasdan ojiz qoldi . Bundan ko'rinib turibdiki, Ali Bazdaviy qomusiy olim hisoblangan. Ali Bazdaviy xalqimizga yot bo'lgan g'oyalar va tahdidlarning kirib kelishiga munosib qarshilik ko'rsata olgan. Bazdaviyini "islomning faxri" deya ulug'lashgan, bundan ko'rinib turibdiki rivojlangan o'rta asrlarda Movarounnahrda islom huquqi rivojlangan. Shunday ekan, o'zga yurtlarda yaratilayotgan, islom huquqining manbalari sifatida e'tirof etilayotgan soxta adabiyotlarga o'rin yo'q.

Hozirgi kunda yoshlarning madaniy va ijtimoiy molashuviga Internet tarmoqlari o'z ta'sirini (ijobiy va salbiy) ko'rsatadi. Internetning yoshlar ongiga ijobiy jixatlari: axborotga ega bo'lish imkoniyati; ta'lim olish imkoniyati; muloqot imkoniyati; o'z-o'zini ifoda etish imkoniyati; ijodiy rivojlanish; ish topish imkoniyati; ijtimoiylashuvdan iborat.

Internetning yoshlar ongiga salbiy jixatlari: depressiv yoshlar oqimi; turli g'arazli g'oyalarni singdirish, narkotiklar, tanishuvlar sayti, aldov, ishonchsizlik; turli karta o'yinlar orqali yoshlarni qimor o'yinlariga o'rgatish, pornografiya; sektalar; ekstremizm, irqchilik, fashizmdan iborat.

"Bugungi kunda Internet orqali shakllantirilayotgan g'oyaviy ta'sir, oshkoro mafkuraviy tayziq oldida xatto tajribali mamlakatlar xam qiyin axvolga tushib qolmoqda. Buning sababi, axborotlashgan ta'sirning an'naviy xavf-xatarlar – terrorchilik, yadroviy qurollarning ishlatilishi, ekologik muammo va boshqalardan farq qilib ko'zga ko'rinmasligi, tezkorligi hamda chegara bilmasligi va xakazo"¹. Bugungi kunda xar qanday salbiy axborotlar ta'siri natijasida turli davlatlar axolisi kayfiyati, ruxiyati dunyoqarashi va xatti-xarakatlarida salbiy o'zgarishlar kuzatilmoqda.

Xozirgi kunga kelib axborot urushi shiddat bilan avj olmoqda. Axborot urushidan ko'zangan asosiy maqsad-turli maqsadlarga erishish uchun raqibga g'oyaviy ta'sir ko'rsatishdir. Shuningdek, axborot xuruji raqibga ta'sir ko'rsatish orqali jamoatchilik ongini g'arazli yo'llar asosida shakllantirishga urinishdir.

¹ Ф.Р.Мадрахимова. "Глобаллашув жараёнида "Оммавий маданият" таҳдидларининг олдини олиш масалалари". Диссертация. – Тошкент 2017 йил.49-бет

Manfaatdor kuchlar axborot xuruji kutilgan natijani berishi uchun yolg'on xabar tarqatish bosimini kuchaytirib, internetni yolg'on ma'lumotlar, soxta iddaolarga to'ldirish kabi usullardan foydalanishadi. Bu ma'lumotlarni o'qigan inson buning manba'sini tekshirib xam o'tirmay ishonib ketishmoqda. Oqibatda, xali oqni qoradan ajratishga ulgurmagan yoshlar internet orqali tarqatilayotgan buzg'unchi ta'limot, g'oyalarga chalg'ib, botil firqalarga qo'shilib qolayotgani achinarli xol! Bunday yoshlar turli saytlardan bilib bilmay ma'lumotlarni ko'chirib olib, o'z e'tiqodi va ongini zaxarlamoqda.

Xozirgi kunga yoshlarda diniy qarashlarning shakllanishi ko'p jixatdan global tarmoq orqali amalga oshirilmoqda.

Nega yendi Internet buzg'unchilar makoniga aylanib qoldi? Buning asosiy sabablari quyidagi omillarda nomoyon bo'ladi:

Birinchidan, Internetning tartibga solinmagani. Internet chegara bilmas va chegarasiz olam xisoblanadi. Bu olamda xar-xil mazmundagi turfa xil ma'lumotlar uchraydi. Internet shu darajada inson qalbi va ongiga ta'sir qiluvchi kuchga aylandiki, unda targ'ib qilinayotgan tartibsiz ma'lumotlarning afzalliklari yoki salbiy oqibatlarini ajratib olish juda qiyin masala.

Ikkinchidan, Internet faoliyatining maxfiyligi. Internet tarmog'ini bekorga "o'rgimchak to'riga" qiyoslanmaydi. Chunki internet xam o'z o'ljasini o'zining to'riga o'rab oladi. Bu o'rgimchak to'rda faoliyat olib borayotgan shaxslar anonim, ya'ni yashirin holatda ham faoliyat olib borishlari mumkin. Bu kabi maxfiy faoiyatning g'oyaviy tazyiqi va ta'sirining o'ziga xosligi shundaki, bunda "maqsadli ish" o'quvchi, tinglovchi yoki tomoshabinga sezdirilmasdan, zimdan amalga oshiriladi.

Uchinchidan, Matn, tasvir va ovoz uyg'unligidagi axborotni joylash kabi qulayliklar. Bu olamda dastlab ma'lumotlar matn ko'rinishida bo'lgan bo'lsa, xozirga kelib internetda nafaqat matn, balki fotolavxa, videolavxa va ovoz uyg'unligidagi ma'lumotlarni joylashtirish va ularni elektron manzillarga jo'natish ham mumkin.

To'rtinchidan, Internetga kirish osonligi. Bugungi kunga kelib internetdan foydalanish juda xam qulay bo'lib qoldi. Bunda nafaqat kompyuter, balki zamonaviy planshetlar va uyali aloqa vositalari, ya'ni telefonlar orqali ham kirib foydalanish imkoniyati mavjud.

Beshinchidan, Cheksiz auditoriya. Global internet tarmog'ida turli fikr va qarashdagi milliardlab insonlar mavjud. Bu sarxadsiz olamda kishilar turli mavzularda fikr almashadi, o'zaro baxs-munozaralar qiladi. Bunday odamlar gavju go'shadan unumli foydalanish uchun g'araz niyatli odamlar virtual makonni o'zlarining "ov makoni"ga aylantirib olmoqda.

Oltinchidan, Ma'lumotlarni yetkazish tezkorligi. Internet orqali bir axborotni yashin tezligida dunyoning bir burchagidan narigi burchagiga yetkazish mumkin. Ushbu qulaylikdan, taasufki, terrorchi shaxslar ham o'z manfur maqsadlari yo'lida ustalik bilan foydalanishmoqda.

Misol uchun: Terrorchi tashkilotlardan biri "al-Qoida" o'z targ'ibotining 99 foizini internet orqali amalga oshiradi. 2011 yilning iyun oyida "al-Qoida" tashkiloti internet orqali terrorchilik amaliyotini o'tkazish bo'yicha ko'rsatmalarni o'z gumashtalariga yetkazishga uringani fosh etilgan. Gap shundaki, tashkilotga taaluqli bo'lgan veb-saxifalarning birida foydalanuvchilarga yuklab olish uchun qiziqarli jurnal taklif etilgan bo'lib, uning saxifalaridanoddiy oshxona sharoitida qo'lbola bomba tayyorlashni o'rgatuvchi ko'rsatmalar joy olgan. Shu orqali tashkilot butun dunyoda o'z a'zolariga o'zini-o'zi portlatish amaliyotlarining so'ngi uslublari haqida ma'lumotlarni yetkazib borgan.²

Ko'rinib turibdiki, axborotlashtirish globallashuv jarayonlari bilan uzviy bog'liq holda kechmoqda. "Bugungi dunyoda mislsiz ilmiy kashfiyotlar, ulkan texnikaviy imkoniyatlar, universal texnologiyalar, axborot tarqatishning globallashuvi, ya'ni ularning butun kurrai zaminni

² А.Тулупов. Интернетдаги таҳдидлардан ҳимоя. Ёрдамчи ўқув қўлланма. "Мовороуннахр" нашриёти, 2015 йил 38-б

qamrab olish jarayoni shiddat bilan bormoqda. Masalan, Internet tizimi orqali axborot almashuv, binobarin, g'oyaviy ta'sir o'tkazish imkoniyatlari xam tobora kengaymoqda. Aslida axborot soxasidagi globallashuv insoniyat uchun, dunyoning barch xududlaridagi odamlarning o'zaro muloqati uchun, ilm-fan va madaniy boyliklarni o'zlashtirish ulkan imkoniyatlar yaratadigan jarayondir".³ Lekin bundan dunyoning ayrim manfaatparast kuchlari millatlar milliy madaniyatini yemiruvchi va axloqsizlikni targ'ib qiluvchi g'oyalarni tarqatish maqsadida foydalanmoqda. Ular ushbu g'oyalarni tarqatishda "ommaviy madaniyat"ni niqob qilib, oson yo'lni izlashmoqda.

Mamlakatimiz yoshlari o'rtasida ularning ma'naviy tarbiyasiga oid so'rovnomalar o'tkazilgan, bu esa yoshlar ongida kechayotgan jarayonlarni chuqurroq ochib berishda muxim ro'l o'ynaydi. Xususan, Internet orqali yoshlar tarbiyasiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatayotgan illatlar va ularning kelib chiqishini o'rganish maqsadida Respublika "Etakchi" yoshlar markazi tomonidan oliy ta'lim muassasalarining 18-25 yoshli talabalari orasida "Internet va yoshlar" mavzusida so'rovnoma o'tkazildi.⁴ Ushbu so'rovnomada asosan, yoshlar ma'naviy ongiga Internet tarmoqlari va ommaviy axborot vositalarining ta'siri haqida savollar berildi. "Siz Internetdan foydalanishga kuniga qancha vaqt sarflaysiz?" savoliga respondentlarning javoblari quyidagicha bo'ldi: 73% resaudent 1-2 soat, 16% respondent 2-3 soat, 7% respondent esa 3-4 soat, vaqtini sarflashlarini aytishgan. 2% respondent Internetdan me'yor darajasidan ko'proq, ya'ni kuniga 4-5 soat foydalanishlari ma'lum bo'lgan. Shuningdek, meyoriy darajadan juda xam oshib ketgan 1% respondent 5-6 soat vaqtini, yana 1% respondentlar esa 7 soat va undan ko'proq vaqtlarini Internetga sarflashlarini aytishgan (1-diagramma)⁵

Respondentlarga "Internetdan foydalanganingizda ko'proq nimaga vaqt sarflaysiz?" savoliga javoblar quyidagicha bo'lindi. Internet o'yinlarini o'ynayman – 5%; Internetdan turli musiqalar, filmlar va o'yinlarni ko'chirib olishda foydalanaman – 4%; Tanishuv saytida yangi do'stlar topaman – 9%; Tanishuv saytlaridan oila qurish maqsadida foydalanaman – 1%; Do'stlarim, qarindoshlarim bilan muloqat qilish uchun – 15%; Shou-biznes, musiqa yulduzlari va san'atdagi mashhur kishilar hayotiga oid shov-shuvli yangiliklarni qidiraman – 6%; Moda, go'zallik, salomatlik va o'zaro munosabatlar to'g'risidagi ayollar Internet jurnallarini o'qiyman – 3%; Pornografik saytlarga kiraman – 4%; Sport yangiliklaridan xabardor bo'laman – 6%; Internetdan jaxon va O'zbekistondagi yangiliklar bilan tanishaman – 8%; O'zbekiston OAV va televideniya yoritilmagan siyosiy va iqtisodiy yangiliklarni izlayman – 2%; Oddiy kitoblar va OAV da uchramaydigan diniy ma'lumotlarni izlayman – 1%; Internetdan uyimdagi kompyuter uchun kerakli dasturlarni ko'chirib olishda foydalanaman – 3%; O'qish va dars berish uchun kerak bo'lgan materiallar, ma'lumotlar, darsliklarni topaman – 25%

Bu tadqiqotlarni taxlil qilgan xolda ularning yuzaga chiqarayotgan omillarni aniqlash va ularga qarshi amaliy choralar ko'rishni ta'lab etadi. Ilmiy saytga kirib, kerakli manbani o'qib turgan paytingizda birdaniga tanishuv yoki pornografik saytlar reklamasi eranda paydo bo'ladi. Ruxiy ta'sir quvvatiga ega bu reklamalarga e'tibor qaratish, ortiqcha ma'lumotlar ortidan quvish inson vaqtini bexuda sarflash demakdir. Shuning uchun, yoshlar virtual olamda nima yaxshi-yu, nima yomonligini o'rganishlari, internetdan to'g'ri foydalanish madaniyatini egallashlari kerak.

REFERENCES

1. Мўйдинов, А. (2021). ЁШЛАРНИ ТУРЛИ ТАХДИДЛАРДАН ҲИМОЯ ҚИЛИШДА АЖДОДЛАР МЕРОСИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(2), 132-137.

³ Миллий истиқлол ғояси: асосий тушунча ва тамойиллар. – Т., Ўзбекистон, 2000 йил

⁴ "Интернет ва ёшлар" "Етакчи" ёшлар маркази томонидан ўтказилган социологик тадқиқотлар. Т., 2013

⁵ Шу тадқиқот

2. Asilbek, M. (2022). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF EDUCATION OF AN ENLIGHTENED PERSON IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY. *Conferencea*, 183-186.
3. Adham o'g'li, M. A. (2022). THE ROLE OF NATIONAL WITCHCRAFT HERITAGE IN THE SPIRITUAL RISE OF SOCIETY (SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS). *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 10, 122-127.
4. Muydinov, A. (2022). Enlightenment in turkestan in the second half of the xix-early xx centuries. Enlightenment by jadid school. *Asia pacific journal of marketing & management review issn: 2319-2836 impact factor: 7.603*, 11(10), 14-20.
5. Ruzmatovich, u. S. (2022). Processes of organization of technical, tactical and physical preparation in national wrestling training. *International journal of research in commerce, it, engineering and social sciences issn: 2349-7793 impact factor: 6.876*, 16(3), 65-68.
6. Ruzmatovich, U. S. (2022). CHANGES EXPECTED TO COME IN OUR LIFE MOVEMENTS. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(3), 485-489.
7. Shohbozjon, K., & Azizjon, M. (2022). PREPARING SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE FIELD OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS BEFORE ENTRY TO HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876*, 16(10), 100-108.
8. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Developing Critical Thinking In Primary School Students. *Conferencea*, 97-102.
9. Oljayevna, O., & Shavkatovna, S. (2020). The Development of Logical Thinking of Primary School Students in Mathematics. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(2), 235-239.
10. Uljaevna, U. F., & Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Development and education of preschool children. *Academicia: an international multidisciplinary research journal*, 11(2), 326-329.
11. Shavkatovna, S. R. N. (2021). Methodical Support Of Development Of Creative Activity Of Primary School Students. *Conferencea*, 74-76.
12. Ra'noxon, S. (2022). BOSHLANG'ICH MAKTAB O'QUVCHILARIDA MATEMATIKAGA MUNOSABAT. *IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 203-207.
13. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Methodological Support for The Development of Primary School Students' Creative Activities. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2, 121-123.
14. Shavkatovna, S. R. (2021). Improvement of methodological pedagogical skills of developing creative activity of primary school students. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(10), 289-292.
15. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдуллаева, С. (2022). ФИКРЛАШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА МЕНТАЛ АРИФМЕТИКА. *IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 235-239.
16. Maxamadaliyevna, Y. D., Òljayevna, Ò. F., Qizi, T. D. T., Shavkatovna, S. R. N., & Anvarovna, A. O. (2020). Pedagogical Features Of Mental Development Of Preschool Children. *Solid State Technology*, 63(6), 14221-14225.

17. Sharofutdinova, R. I., Asadullaev, A. N., & Tolibova, Z. X. (2021). The Factors and Basic Concepts Determining Community Health. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 2(5), 376-379.
18. Iqboljon, S. (2022). Boshlang'ich Sinf o'quv Jarayonida Axborot Texnologiyalaridan Foydalanish. *Ijodkor o'qituvchi*, 2(20), 137-140.
19. Iqboljon, S. (2022). KOMPYUTER YORDAMIDA DARSLARNI TASHKIL ETISH. O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 1(9), 246-249.
20. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS IN THE CONDITIONS OF INFORMING EDUCATION. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(5), 424-429.
21. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). THE ACTUAL STATUS OF THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS IN THE CONDITIONS OF INFORMING EDUCATION. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(12), 206-213.
22. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). BO 'LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNING AKMEOLOGIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASINING AMALIYOTDA QOLLASH. *Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 2(7), 54-58.
23. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). PEDAGOGIK-PSIXOLOGIK FANLARNING BO 'LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNING AKMEOLOGIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDAGI O 'RNI. *Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 2(6), 17-24.
24. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). TA'LIMNI AXBOROTLASHTIRISH SHAROITIDA BO 'LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNING AKMEOLOGIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK TIZIMI. *Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика*, 2(14), 13-19.
25. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). TA'LIMNI AXBOROTLASHTIRISH SHAROITIDA BO 'LAJAK PEDAGOGLARNING AKMEOLOGIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MODELI. *Наука и технология в современном мире*, 2(13), 77-84.
26. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). STRUCTURE AND COMPONENTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF ACMEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE EDUCATORS IN THE CONDITIONS OF EDUCATION INFORMATION. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(4), 574-580.
27. Sharofutdinov, I. (2023). FORMS OF SELF-DEVELOPMENT IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES BASED ON THE ACMEOLOGICAL APPROACH IN THE PROCESS OF INFORMATIZATION OF EDUCATION. *Science and innovation*, 2(B3), 5-8.
28. Usmonjon o'g'li, S. I. (2022). TA'LIM TIZIMIDA RAQAMLI TEXNALOGIYA. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 120-128.
29. Абдужабборов, А., & Шарофутдинова, Р. (2023). БОШЛАНГИЧ СИНФ ЎҚУВЧИЛАРИДА ИЖОДИЙ ФАОЛИЯТНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШГА ҚАРАТИЛГАН ТАЪЛИМ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРИ.
30. Sharofutdinova, R., & Abduqodirov, B. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 904-910.

31. Sharafutdinova, R., & Abdujabborov, A. (2023). EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES AIMED AT THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 890-896.
32. Шарофутдинова, Р. (2023). ИЖОД ТУШУНЧАСИ ФАОЛИЯТНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ МЕХАНИЗМИ. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 2(19), 854-861.
33. Шарофутдинова, Р. (2023). БОШЛАНГИЧ СИНФ ЎҚУВЧИЛАРИНИНГ ИЖОДИЙ ФАОЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ-ИЖТИМОЙ ПЕДАГОГИК ЗАРУРАТ СИФАТИДА. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 2(19), 842-847.
34. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдуқодиров, Б. (2023). ТЕХНОЛОГИК ТАЪЛИМ ЖАРАЁНИДА ЎҚУВЧИЛАРИНИНГ ИЖОДИЙ ФАОЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ОМИЛЛАРИ ВА ТАМОЙИЛЛАРИ. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 2(19), 862-868.
35. Шарофутдинова, Р., & Абдужабборов, А. (2023). ТЕХНОЛОГИК ТАЪЛИМНИНГ ИЖОДИЙ ЙЎНАЛТИРИЛГАНЛИГИДА ҲАМКОРЛИК КЛАСТЕРИ. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 2(19), 848-853.
36. Shavkatovna, S. R. N., & Sohiboxon, S. (2023). MAXSUS TA'LIMNING RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 2(19), 830-836.
37. Ra'noxon, S., Mahpuza, A., & Rahmatjonzoda, A. (2022). THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF LOGICAL THINKING WITH THE HELP OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(11), 881-885.
38. Mahpuza, A., & Rahmatjonzoda, A. (2022). THE USE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MATHEMATICS LESSONS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(11), 213-217.
39. Maxamadaliyevna, Y. D., & O'ljayevna, O. R. F. (2020). Tursunova Dilnavoz To 'lqin qizi, Sharofutdinova Ra'noxon Shavkatovna, Ashurova Oygul Anvarovna. Pedagogical features of mental development of preschool children. *Solid State Technology*, 63(6).
40. Mirzaxolmatovna, X. Z., Nematovna, R. S., & Shavkatovna, S. R. (2022). FORMS OF THINKING IN THE PROCESS OF STUDYING MATHEMATICS. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(12), 259-263.
41. Ganiev, A. A., Abdullaev, S. Y., & Abdurahmonov, S. Z. (2021). Combined treatment for early-stage skin cancer of the head and neck area. *World Bulletin of Public Health*, 4, 3-6.
42. Ganiev, A. A., & kizi Ganieva, O. O. TASAVVUF TARIQATI YO 'NALISHLARI VA NAQSHBANDIYA TARIQATINING O 'ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI.
43. Ruzmatovich, U. S., & Shohbozjon G'ayratjon o'g, Q. (2023). Uzbekistan's General Education School Physical Education Programme: A Curriculum Analysis. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(5), 184-193.
44. Ruzmatovich, U. S., & Shohbozjon G'ayratjon o'g, Q. (2023). Examining the First Age Group's Health Test Needs for "Salomatlik" Regulation Using the Dynamic of Children's Motor Potential. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(5), 194-200.

45. Kosimov, K., & Mamayusupov, J. (2019). Transitions melline integral of fractional integrodifferential operators. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 1(1), 12-15.
46. Qo'Ziyev, S. S., & Mamayusupov, J. S. (2021). Umumiy o'rtta ta'lim maktablari uchun elektron darslik yaratishning pedagogik shartlari. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(10), 447-453.
47. Мамаюсупов, Ж. Ш. (2022). Интегральное преобразование Меллина для оператора интегродифференцирования дробного порядка. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 11, 186-188.
48. Mamayusupov, J. S. O. (2022). "IQTISOD" YO'NALISHI MUTAXASSISLARINI TAYYORLASHDA MATEMATIKA FANINI O'QITISH USLUBIYOTI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(3), 720-728.
49. Mamayusupov, J., & Sattarov, A. (2022). Mellin Integral Replacement and its Applications. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 15, 256-263.
50. Shoyunus o'g'li, M. J. (2023). PISA XALQARO BAHOLASH TIZIMI VA UNING MATEMATIK AHAMIYATI. *Journal of new century innovations*, 25(1), 3-8.
51. Shoyunus o'g'li, M. J. (2023). MATEMATIK MODEL VA MATEMATIK MODELLASHTIRISHNING UMUMIY PRINSIPLARI. *World scientific research journal*, 13(1), 45-48.
52. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). Basic theoretical principles of corpus linguistics. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(2), 1-3.
53. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). LINGVISTIK TADQIQOTLARDA KORPUS O'RGANISH OBYEKTI SIFATIDA. IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(11), 176-182.
54. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGVISTIKA VA UNING TAHLILY SHAKLLANISH TARIXI. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 99-105.
55. Vosiljonov, A. (2022). PRAGMALINGUISTICS AND THE HISTORY OF ITS ANALYTICAL DEVELOPMENT. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 99-105.
56. Vosiljonov, A., & Isaqova, X. (2023). EFFECTIVENESS OF MOTHER TONGUE EDUCATION IN THE PRIMARY GRADES. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(2).
57. KHALIMBOYEVA, F., & VOSILJONOV, A. (2023). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALAR DIQQATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MUAMMOSINI NAZARIY O'RGANILISHI. *Journal of Pedagogical and Psychological Studies*, 1(5), 94-98.
58. Soxibov, S. (2023). THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IS A HUGE TASK. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 1037-1041.
59. Soxibov, S. (2023). MEASURES TO FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 1031-1036.
60. Anvar o'g'li, S. S. (2023). PHILOSOPHICAL-ANALYTICAL ANALYSIS OF CONFLICT OF INTEREST AND PREVENTION OF CORRUPT RELATIONS. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(3).
61. Anvar o'g'li, S. S. (2021, April). THE ROLE OF RELIGIOUS AND MORAL EDUCATION IN THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION, ALONG WITH THE USE OF ECONOMIC AND LEGAL FACTORS. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 55-57).

62. Нажмиддинов, Э., & Мухамедиев, М. (2023). FISH HELMINTHS IN FISH RESERVOIRS OF FERGANA VALLEY. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(3).
63. Нажмиддинов, Э. Х., & Мухаммадиев, М. А. (2022). ФАРФОНА ВОДИЙСИ СУВ ҲАВЗАЛАРИ БАЛИҚЛАРИ ГЕЛЬМИНТЛАРИНИНГ ТУР ТАРКИБИ. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 60-68.
64. Нажмиддинов, Э. Х. (2022). ФАРФОНА ВОДИЙСИ СУВ ҲАВЗАЛАРИ БАЛИҚЛАРИ ГЕЛЬМИНТЛАРИ. *IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 189-194.
65. Najmiddinov, E. (2022). THE SIGNIFICANCE OF NATURE IN THE FORMATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE IDEAL GENERATION. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 149-154.
66. Najmiddinov, E. (2022). " ICHTHYOLOGY AND HYDROBIOLOGY" PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF DIRECTIONS IN UZBEKISTAN. *Science and Innovation*, 1(8), 152-160.
67. Abidjanovich, A. A. (2022). THE NEED TO IMPROVE HUMAN'S NOOSPHERICAL RELATIONSHIP TO NATURE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11(11), 23-30.
68. Abidjanovich, A. A. (2022). THE ROLE OF CONTINUOUS EDUCATION SYSTEM IN IMPROVING PERSONAL ECOLOGICAL CULTURE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11(11), 5-12.
69. Абдумаликов, А. (2022). АТРОФ-МУҲИТНИ АСРАШ БЎЙИЧА МИЛЛИЙ СТРАТЕГИК РЕЖА ВА УНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(2), 251-258.
70. Абдумаликов, А. (2022). ЯНГИ ТАРАҚҚИЁТ БОСҚИЧИДА ЭКОЛОГИК МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯЛАШ ДАСТУРИ. *Scientific progress*, 3(2), 1179-1186.
71. Абдумаликов, А. А. (2019). Human and Natural Harmony in the Historical Process. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 1(5), 205-209.
72. Abidzhanovich, A. A. (2020). Issues Of Formation Of Rationality In Relations Of Nature With Society. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 2(08), 301-304.
73. Abdumalikov, A. A. (2019). Environmental Ecological Policy in Uzbekistan and Necessity Of Formation Of Rational Communication To Nature. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 1(9), 94-101.
74. Мирзобоев, Й. А. (2022). Тур Ўзгариш Чизиқлари Учта Бўлган, Гиперболик Қисмларининг Ҳаммаси Харақтеристик Учбурчаклардан Иборат Бўлган Бешбурчакли Соҳада Учтинчи Тартибли Кўринишдаги Параболик-Гиперболик Тенглама Учун Битта Чегаравий Масала Ҳақида. *Theory And Analytical Aspects Of Recent Research*, 1(5), 363-366.
75. Mirzaboyev, y. Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining matematika o 'qitish metodikasi. O 'rta umumta'lim maktablarida matematika o 'qitishning maqsadi. *Экономика*, 169-172.
76. Iminov, B. B. (2020). INNOVATIVE CULTURAL LINKS ARE AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 2(3), 263-270.

77. Iminov, B. B. (2019). A PHILOSOPHICAL APPROACH TO INNOVATIVE AND CULTURAL-RELATIONS AT A NEW STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 1(5), 157-162.
78. Qizi, S. G. G. O. (2022). LINGUISTIC BASIS AND PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF TEACHING WORD MEANING TO PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(12), 117-123.
79. Qizi, S. G. G., & Teshaboyevna, D. D. Methods Of Formation Of Independent Reading Skills In Primary School Pupils. *JournalNX*, 21-24.
80. Kizi, S. G. G. (2021). Formation Of Independent Reading Skills in Primary School Students. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2, 222-224.
81. Valijonovna, K. I., Rakhmatjonovich, T. D., & Mukhtoralievna, Z. S. (2022). Informational Technology at Education. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 6, 262-266.
82. Akmaljonovna, A. Z. (2021). Methods of formation of independent reading skills in primary school students. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 1425-1428.
83. Dehqonova, M., & Tagonova, G. (2022). The Importance of Didactic Games in Speech Therapy in the Development of Speech in Children with Autism and the Ability to Choose Effective Methods. *European Journal of Innovation In Nonformal Education*, 2(1), 133-137.
84. Dehqonova, M. (2022). BOLALARDAGI YOZUV BUZILISHLARI VA ULARDAGI DISGRAFIYADA O 'ZIGA XOS XATOLIKLARNI PAYDO BO 'LISH MEXANIZMI. YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA MILLIY TARAQQIYOT VA INNOVASIYALAR, 405-407.
85. Dehqonova, M., & Najmiddinova, N. (2022). ALOHIDA EHTIYOJGA EGA BO'LGAN BOLALARNING OILAGA MOSLASHISHI UCHUN MUHIM OMILLAR. YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA MILLIY TARAQQIYOT VA INNOVASIYALAR, 90-92.
86. Dehqonova, M. (2023). MAXSUS MAKTABDA DAKTIL NUTQINI O'QITISH-TADQIQOT OBYEKTI SIFATIDA. *Наука и инновация*, 1(1), 39-40.
87. Qizi, D. M. S., & Qizi, R. G. X. (2022). METHODS OF STUDYING ADDITION AND SUBTRACTION OF TWO-DIGIT NUMBERS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 22, 61-67.
88. Dehqonova, M. S. Q., & Axmedova, U. Y. Q. (2023). BO 'LAJAK BOSHLANG 'ICH SINF O 'QITUVCHILARINI MATEMATIK SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH JARAYONIDA ULARNING TAFAKKURI, QOBILIYATI VA INTELLEKTUAL RIVOJLANISH. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(4-2), 251-256.
89. Otazonov, S. M., Ergashev, R. N., Botirov, K. A., Qaxxorova, B. A., Xudoynazarova, M. A., Abdulkarimova, N. A., ... & Ismoilova, E. M. (2022, December). Influence of thickness and temperature on photoelectric properties of p-CdTe-nCdS and pCdTe-CdSe heterostructures. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 2388, No. 1, p. 012001). IOP Publishing.
90. Otazonov, S. M., Ergashev, R. N., Axmedov, T., Usmonov, Y., & Karimov, B. (2022, December). Photoelectric properties of solar cells based on pCdTe-nCdS and pCdTe-nCdSe heterostructures. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 2388, No. 1, p. 012062). IOP Publishing.

91. Abdulvakhidov, K., Li, Z., Abdulvakhidov, B., Soldatov, A., Otajonov, S., Ergashev, R., ... & Sitalo, E. (2023). Structure phase state and physical properties of YbMn_{1-x}Fe_xO₃ compositions. *Applied Physics A*, 129(3), 185.
92. Ahmedova, U. Y. Q., & Axmedova, M. U. B. Q. (2021). Vatanim Surati. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(11), 877-883.
93. Axmedova, U. (2022). On Certain Conditions Of Striking Coefficients Of Fourier Series To Zero. *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*, 3(3), 3-8.
94. Qizi, A. U. Y., & Qizi, A. M. U. B. (2021). Research On Hydronyms and Their Importance.
95. Umidaxon, A., & Gulirano, S. (2023). BOSHLANG'ICH SINF MATEMATIKA DARSLARIDA AMALIY MASHQLAR YECHISH JARAYONIDA O'QUVCHILARNING FIKRLASH QOBILIYATINI OSTIRISH OMILLARI. *PEDAGOGIKA, PSIXOLOGIYA VA IJTIMOIIY TADQIQOTLAR*, 2(5), 10-14.
96. Axmedov, O. U. B. O. G., & Qizi, A. U. Y. (2022). STEREOOMETRIYA BO'LIMI VA UNING BA'ZI AKSIOMALARIDAN KELIB CHIQUADIGAN NATIJALAR. *International scientific journal of Biruni*, 1(2), 127-133.
97. Axmedova, U. Y. Q., & Axmedova, M. U. B. Q. (2022). XALQ OG 'ZAKI IJOD NAMUNALARINING BOSHLANG 'ICH SINF DARSLIKLARIDA QO 'LLANISHI VA ULARNING MAZMUNIIY GURUHLANISHI. *International scientific journal of Biruni*, 1(2), 345-351.
98. Erkinovna, N. S. (2022). Educational Methods in Teaching the Russian Language. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 260-263.
99. Erkinovna, N. S. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF LISTENING SKILLS IN LEARNING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 1(12), 138-145.
100. Erkinovna, N. S. (2022). MECHANISMS OF EFFECTIVE TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES USING INNOVATIVE METHODS. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 11, 132-135.
101. Erkinovna, N. S. (2023). RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN THE MODERN WORLD. *Open Access Repository*, 4(3), 284-295.
102. Rakhmatdjonov Shokhjahan Dilshodbek o'g'li //THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL CULTURE IN PROVIDING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH OF THE ATHLETE// INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION. International scientific online conference. Canada. Part 2, 23.01.2022. 1-3
103. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahan Dilshodbek o'g'li //SPORTCHI PSIXOLOGIK SALOMATLIGIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR// GALAXY INTERNATIONAL INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL (GIIRJ). Vol. 10, Issue 11, Nov.(2022). 117-121 pages.
104. QURBONOVA Saida Miralimjanovna, RAXMATJONOV Shoxjahan Dilshodbek o'g'li //MAMLAKATIMIZ PSIXOLOGLARI ISHLARIDA SHAXSLARARO MUNOSABATDA MUOMALA MUAMMOSINING TALQINI// Journal of Pedagogical and Psychological Studies. Vol. 1. № 5, (2023). 99-103 pages.
105. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahan Dilshodbek o'g'li //SPEECH ISSUES IN PSYCHOLINGUISTICS// IQRO JURNALI № 2. 04.2023. 503-511 betlar.
106. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahan Dilshodbek o'g'li, Vosiljonov Azizbek Boxodirjon o'g'li //XORIJ PSIXOLOGLARINING ISHLARIDA SHAXSNING TADQIQ ETILISHI//

- INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION. Vol. 1. № 12, 2022. 39-47 pages.
107. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li //TALABALARDA TOLERANTLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH – IJTIMOY PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA// International Journal of Economy and Innovation. Volume: 30. 2022. 66-70 pages.
 108. Rakhmatdjonov Shokhjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li //PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE SPORTSMAN PERSONALITY DURING COMPETITIONS// IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMYIY JURNALI. Vol. 2 No. 11 (2022). 215-221 betlar.
 109. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li //Motiv Va Motivatsiya Muammosining Jahon Va Mahalliy Psixologlar Tomonidan Tadqiq Etilganligi// American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, Vol. 3 No. 11 (2022). 256-259 pages.
 110. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li //TOLERANTLIK SHAKLLANAYOTGAN SHAXS MODELINING TAVSIFI// International scientific journal «MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH». VOLUME 2 / ISSUE 5 /2023. 761-764 pages.
 111. Raxmatjonov Shoxjahon Dilshodbek o'g'li. (2023). PSIXOLOGIYADA MOTIVATSIYA TURLARI, NAZARIYALARI VA TAHLILI. Научный Импульс, 1(10), 665-670.
 112. Raximov, Q., & Samijonov, A. (2023). DESCRIPTION OF WAYS TO BUILD A SELF-SIMILAR SOLUTION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 950-958.
 113. Raximov, Q., & Samijonov, A. (2023). DESCRIPTION OF PROCESSES WITH CONVECTIVE TRANSPORT. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 941-949.
 114. Kadirov, S. (2023). HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL MONUMENTS AND THEIR CONDITION IN FERGANA REGION (1991-2020 IN THE CASE OF THE CITY OF MARGILAN): THE ISSUE OF PRESERVATION, PROTECTION AND THEIR USE. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 818-830.
 115. Abduraxmonov, a., & kadirov, s. (2022). Demografik jarayonlarning iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy sohalarni rivojlanishi bilan bog 'liqligi va dastlabki xususiy mulk masalalari. *Ijtimoiy fanlarda innovasiya onlayn ilmiy jurnali*, 2(11), 222-229.
 116. Yo'lichiboyeva, L. (2023). METHODS FOR GROWING SPEECH SKILLS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 1028-1030.
 117. Yo'lichiboyeva, L. (2023). METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING THE NOUN PHRASE CATEGORY: ENHANCING LANGUAGE LEARNING IN STUDENTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 1025-1027.
 118. Kalandarovna, Y. L. (2023). Superstitions in Linguoculturology. *DENMARK" THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS IN MODERN SOCIETY"*, 14(1).
 119. Qalandarovna, Y. L. L. (2023). O 'QUVCHILAR NUTQINI O 'STIRISH METODIKASI. *IQRO JURNALI*, 2(2), 637-645.
 120. Qalandarovna, Y. L. L. (2023). LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK BIRLIKLARNING NUTQDAGI O'RNI. *IQRO*, 2(2), 522-529.
 121. Kalandarovna, Y. L. (2022). ORIGIN AND CONCEPT OF TABOO VOCABULARY. *Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal*, 3(10), 184-190.